

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS ON THE EFFECT OF PRESSURE SPRINGS GENERATING THE PRESSURE FORCE APPLIED TO THE SUPPORT DISC INSTALLED ON A DISC PLOUGH ON ITS OPERATING PERFORMANCE

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Аннотация. В статье представлены результаты экспериментальных исследований влияния силы давления, прикладываемой к опорному диску, на эксплуатационные показатели дискового плуга. Установлено, что при силе давления на опорный диск, равной 500 кН, опорная сила была недостаточной, в результате чего фактическая ширина захвата плуга при отвальной вспашке превышала конструктивную ширину захвата на 6,3 и 8,2 см. При использовании нажимных пружин, обеспечивающих силу давления 500 кН, наблюдалось боковое отклонение плуга в процессе работы. При увеличении силы давления, прикладываемой к опорному диску, до 600–700 кН плуг работал без бокового отклонения, вследствие чего его фактическая ширина захвата практически совпадала с конструктивной шириной захвата.

Ключевые слова: ширина захвата, среднеквадратическое отклонение, высота неровностей поверхности, удельное тяговое сопротивление, пружина, рабочая скорость.

Abstract. This paper presents the results of experimental studies on the influence of the pressure force applied to the support disc on the operating performance of a disc plough. The experiments showed that when the pressure force applied to the support disc was 500 kN, the supporting force was insufficient, which caused the actual working width of the plough to exceed the design working width by 6.3 and 8.2 cm during mouldboard-type ploughing. Under the same pressure force of 500 kN, the use of pressure springs led to lateral deviation of the plough during operation. When the pressure force applied to the support disc was increased to 600-700 kN, the plough operated without lateral deviation; as a result, its actual working width was almost identical to the design working width.

Keywords: working width, root mean square deviation, surface roughness height, specific draft resistance, spring, operating speed.

Introduction. In recent years, the widespread implementation of energy- and resource-saving technologies and technical means in agriculture has significantly increased the importance of using disc ploughs for primary tillage (ploughing). In such ploughs, the working bodies are designed in the form of spherical discs. Compared to mouldboard ploughs, disc ploughs exhibit lower draft resistance, higher operational productivity, and stable performance without clogging by crop residues and weeds [1].

Research methodology. The experiments were conducted on an experimental field of the institute that had been previously cultivated with winter wheat. The tests were carried out on wheat-harvested plots of the QXMITI experimental site, which had been irrigated prior to the experiments.

Table 2 presents the characteristics of the field soil prior to the experiments, including soil moisture

content, soil hardness, and the amount and height of stubble.

During the experimental investigations, a disc plough equipped with a support disc device was operated in combination with a New Holland TD5.110 tractor. The specific draft resistance of the unit was determined using strain-gauge sensors in accordance with O'zDSt 3193:2017 "Testing of agricultural machinery. Method for energy evaluation of machines". The agrotechnical performance indicators were determined in accordance with O'zDSt 3412:2019 "Testing of agricultural machinery. Machines and implements for soil surface tillage. Test program and methods" [2–4].

Results of the study. During the experiments, the diameter of the support disc was set to 450 mm, the pressure force applied to the support disc was up to 700 kN, and the installation angle of the support disc relative to the vertical was 20°. The drawbar length was 80 cm, the tillage depth was fixed at 30 cm, and the operating speed of the unit was set to 6 and 9 km/h.

The experimental results obtained from the study of the influence of variations in the pressure springs generating the pressure force applied to the support disc on the agrotechnical and energy performance of the disc plough are presented in Table 1 and Figures 1–4. The results show that when the pressure force applied to the support disc was 500 kN, the spring compression force and the force acting on the support disc were insufficient. As a consequence, the supporting force was inadequate, and during mouldboard-type ploughing the actual working width of the plough exceeded the design working width.

In this case, the range of variation reached relatively high values. This can be explained by the fact that an increase in the pressure force applied to the support disc significantly affected the width of the soil clods being processed. When the pressure force applied to the support disc was increased from 600 to 700 kN, the plough operated without lateral deviation; therefore, its actual working width was almost identical to the design working width.

Further analysis shows that at a pressure force of 500 kN, the insufficient supporting force caused the actual working width of the plough during mouldboard-type ploughing to exceed the design working width by 6.3 and 8.2 cm, respectively. This indicates that the use of springs providing a pressure force of 500 kN leads to lateral deviation of the plough during operation.

When the pressure force applied to the support disc was in the range of 600–700 kN, the plough operated without lateral deviation; consequently, its actual working width was almost identical to the design working width.

Table 1

Effect of pressure springs generating the pressure force applied to the support disc on the operating performance of the disc plough

Pressure force applied to the support disc, kN	Plough working width, cm	Root mean square deviation of working width, cm	Height of surface irregularities on the ploughed field, cm	Specific draft resistance of the plough, kN/m
V=6 km/h				
500	96,3	6,7	8,2	8,20
600	93,4	4,5	5,4	7,14
700	92,2	4,9	4,5	6,25

800	95,1	6,4	6,7	8,27
V=9 km/h				
500	98,2	7,7	7,8	9,20
600	96,3	6,4	6,5	8,22
700	96,6	6,6	6,7	7,29
800	98,5	7,4	7,5	9,10

Table 2

Characteristics of the experimental field

No	Characteristics of the experimental field	Value
1.	Soil moisture by layers (cm), %: 0-10 10-20 20-30	12,2 15,3 17,4
2.	Soil hardness by layers (cm), MPa: 0-10 10-20 20-30	0,64 1,83 2,89
3.	Depth of irrigation furrows, cm: M_o $\pm s$	14,8 2,4
4.	Crop residues per 1 m ² , kg:	0,492
5.	Stubble height, cm: M_o $\pm s$	24,4 4,3

6 km/h (a)

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Figure 1.

Variation of the plough working width (M_{or}) and the root mean square deviation of the working width ($\pm\sigma$) as a function of the pressure force applied to the support disc (P_r).

9 km/h (b)

Figure 3. Variation of the plough working width (M_{or}) and the root mean square deviation of the working width ($\pm\sigma$) as a function of the pressure force applied to the support disc (P_r).

Figure 2.

Variation of the surface irregularity height of the ploughed field ($H_{\gamma uZ}$) and the specific draft resistance of the plough (R) as a function of the pressure force applied to the support disc (P_r).

9 km/h (b)

Figure 4. Variation of the surface irregularity height of the ploughed field ($H_{\gamma uZ}$) and the specific draft resistance of the plough (R) as a function of the pressure force applied to the support disc (P_r).

When the pressure force applied to the support disc was increased from 700 to 800 kN, a pronounced effect on the working width was observed.

This is explained by the fact that increasing the pressure force from 700 to 800 kN led to an increase in the force exerted by the support disc on the bottom of the furrow.

As a result, the actual working width of the plough exceeded the design working width, and the tillage depth was also adversely affected. An increase in the operating speed from 6 to 9 km/h similarly resulted in an increase in the plough working width and a reduction in the height of surface irregularities on the ploughed field, while simultaneously causing an increase in the specific draft resistance of the plough.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the conducted study, it was established that, in order to ensure uniform operation of the disc plough in terms of working width, the pressure force applied to the support disc should not exceed 700 kN.

In addition, the findings demonstrate that both insufficient and excessive pressure forces applied to the support disc adversely affect the operational performance of the disc plough. At lower pressure levels, lateral deviation of the plough occurs, leading to increased variability in working width,

whereas excessive pressure results in an undesired increase in working width and negatively influences tillage depth. Therefore, maintaining the pressure force within the optimal range of 600–700 kN ensures stable operation, improved agrotechnical performance, and reduced energy consumption during ploughing.

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